

On the Construction of t- Steiner Quintuple Systems of Balanced Incomplete Block Designs

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Abstract

Design tuples for a t-Steiner Quintuple Systems of balanced incomplete block designs or Steiner system of balanced incomplete block design with blocks having five elements with t and λ varied and the order, n and the cardinality p , kept constant were generated and tested using the divisibility theorem for t-designs. The design tuples that satisfied the divisibility theorem and those that do not satisfy it were classified as Obedient Designs and Non-obedient designs respectively. Exploration and construction on the group of Obedient Designs were carried out and the results showed that some obedient designs do not exist at all and hence cannot be constructed but t up to p , the cardinality and λ up to $p-1$ designs exist. The interesting discoveries and result are as summarized.

Keywords: *Cyclic or difference set, Design tuples, Divisibility Theorem, Steiner Systems.*

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Introduction

Balanced Incomplete Block Design

A block design is a non-empty $N = \{n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_m\}$ whose elements are varieties and a non-empty collection of subsets of b blocks of size p with each of the elements replicated or appears r times in the blocks. When the copious numbers of similar experimental units are not accessible to contain all the treatments in block, then the use of incomplete block design is applied. A block design is incomplete if the number of varieties is greater than the block size, that is $(p < n)$ (Akra et al., 2024, 2025).

An incomplete block design is said to be balanced when its consist of a set of points N that is divided into b subsets in such a way that each point in N is contained in r different subsets and the couple of points in N is contained in $(\lambda < b)$ subsets with $(p < n)$ points in each subset. A Balanced Incomplete Block Design (BIBD) is traditionally known by the parameters n, p, r, b, λ where n is the varieties or elements, p is the block size, r is the number each element is replicated in the blocks, b is the total number of blocks and λ is the pair of treatment. These parameters are

connected by the formula $bp = nr$ and $\lambda(n-1) = r(k-1)$ known as the Fisher's formula (Fisher, 1940). See (Umoren & Isaac, 2010, Isaac et al., 2025, 2025; Anthony, E 2018) for the construction of balanced designs and (Akra et al., 2021; 2023, 2025, 2025, 2025.) for the approaches to construction of BIBDs and structures of BIBDs. See (Michael et al., 2017, 2025; Usen et al., 2021).

Steiner Systems

Steiner Systems of balanced incomplete block designs are special balanced incomplete block designs that is concerned with the number of elements in the block. It was first proposed and constructed by Sir Jacob Steiner (1853) and studied by Plucker (1835), Kirkman (1857), Cayley (1850), Bay and de Weck (1935), Bose (1939; 1942a), Skolen (1958), Hannani (1961; 1975) and reported by the Encyclopedia of design theory (2004). The Steiner Systems written as $S(N) - BIBD$ could be traced or is said to have its origin from the early general existence result given by Rev. T.P. Kirkman while answering the question posed by Woolhouse in the price question of "Lady's and Gentleman's Diary" of 1733. The question was "Determine the number of combinations that can be made of n symbols, p symbols in each, with this limitation, that no combination of q symbols which may appear in any one of them shall be repeated in any other". Kirkman (1857) showed that the triple (3 elements in the block) system of order n exists and is balanced if and only if $n \equiv 1, 3 \pmod{6}$. Steiner (1835) studied the triple system, that is, $S(n, 3, \lambda)$ and came up with Kirkman's result independently. He proposed the problem of arranging 'n' objects in triplets such that every pair of objects appears in precisely one triplet. That arrangement is a balanced incomplete block design and because his work was more broadly disseminated in mathematical circles, the triple system was named after him. He proved the necessary conditions for the existence of STS(n) using the same arguments as for BIBDs and also showed that the total number of pairs, the total number of triples or blocks, b and the number of replication, r is $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$, $\frac{n(n-1)}{6}$ and $\frac{n-1}{2}$ respectively. He equally showed that n must be of the form, $6k+1$ for some $k \geq 1$ if the system must exist. Others who worked on the triple system include Moore (1893).

The study of Steiner triple systems started with STS(n, p, λ) for $n = 7$ and 9 , p or block size or cardinality as 3 and $\lambda = 1$. By extending the work further, STS(n) of other orders such as $19, 21$ etc and λ increased from one to two were proved of their existences and subsequently constructed. Nevertheless, in all the extended and constructed designs, p was a constant 3 . It was Moore (1896) that posed the problem of the existence of a Steiner quadruple systems, SQS(v, p, λ) in which $p = 4$ in his paper, "Tactical Memoranda". Barrau (1908) worked on it and established the uniqueness and existence of the $p = 4$ family of BIBDs. He equally constructed $S(8, 4, 3)$ and $S(10, 4, 3)$ which is a $6k + 2$ and $6k + 4$ for $k = 1$ respectively as was later shown by Hannani (1954). Fitting (1915) made an in roads and constructed $S(26, 4, 3)$ and $S(34, 4, 3)$ using the cyclic approach. Bays and de Weck (1935) followed the work of Moore and proved the existence of at least one $(14, 4, 3)$.

The greatest breakthrough in the study of the Steiner quadruple systems came, when Hanani (1960) gave the necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of such a system to be $n \equiv 2$ or $4 \pmod{6}$ which can be interpreted as $n = 6k + 2$ or $6k + 4$. This means that, unlike the triple systems, n for the $p = 4$ systems must not be an odd number. The work of Hannani opened the floodgates for several researches on the $p = 4$ Steiner systems. It also raised curiosity on the study of the quintuple or $p = 5$ family of the Steiner systems called the Steiner quintuple systems.

Steiner Quintuple Systems

A Steiner System, $S(n, p, \lambda) - BIBDs$ in which p or cardinality or block size is 5 is called a Steiner quintuple system and there are quite a few literature in the quintuple systems of balanced incomplete design. Again, the man behind the introduction of the $p = 5$ Steiner systems is Hanani

(1972) and because it follows the Steiner systems, it was called the Steiner quintuple systems written as $S(n, 5, \lambda)$. He gave the necessary (not sufficient) condition for the existence of such a system as $n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ which comes from considerations that applies to all the classical Steiner systems. An additional necessary condition is that $n \not\equiv 4 \pmod{5}$, which comes from the fact that the number of blocks must be an integer. Hannai (1954) also proved that for balanced incomplete block designs with blocks having five elements each ($p = 5$), the known necessary existence condition is also sufficient, with the exception of the non-existing design $S(15, 5, 2)$. Nevertheless, the sufficient condition for the quintuple family of Steiner systems is still under investigation. This is so because there is a quintuple of order 11, that is, $n = 6k + 5$ for $k = 1$ but there is no quintuple of order 17, that is, $n = 6k + 5$ for $k = 2$. There are quintuple for order 23, that is for $k = 3$, but no quintuple for order 29, that is, $k = 4$, there is a quintuple for order 35, that is, for $k = 5$, but there is no quintuple for order 41, that is, $k = 6$ etc. Unlike the triple and quadruple systems where at least λ and n have been varied, work on the quintuple only revolves around the order n .

The t- Steiner Systems Designs

It has been established that in a BIBD, every pair $\{x, y\}$ appears together λ times. This pair is what is referred to as t . Though initially, this pair was equal to two in the early designs like in Kirkman (7,3,1), Bose (9,3,1), Steiner (7, 3,1) Designs, Kirkman (7, 3, 2) and Denniston (15, 3, 2) designs, yet, since it was not regarded as an important parameter, it was not attached to other BIBD parameters. While the parameters of all BIBDs including the Steiner systems BIBDs are supposed to incorporate t so that BIBD would be written as t - (n, p, λ) -BIB designs, yet, that was never the case. In those early designs, it was (n, p, b, r, λ) -BIBDs.

The study of t - designs is of recent. Authors like Earl Krasmer and Dale Menser (1976), Wilson (1973), Ho Y. S and Mendelsohn (1974) and Hananni (1975) attempted to link the parameters of the BIBD with t and mentioned it passively but did not do an in-depth study on it. The most useful result on t - design was given by Peter Keevash (2014) when he proposed the natural divisibility conditions for a t - (n, p, λ) -BIBD and gave it to be $\binom{p-i}{t-i} / \lambda \binom{n-i}{t-i}$. This is largely reported by Joy Moris in her book, Combinatorics (2021) where he posited that the divisibility theorem is a necessary condition for the existence of t - systems of designs. He further argued that the designs that do not obey the divisibility theorem does not exist. From this theorem, the relationship between t, b, p, r and λ was given (see chapter three).

Therefore a t -design or t -Steiner systems of balanced incomplete block design written as t - (n, p, λ) -BIB design, is a pair (X, B) , where X is an n -set of elements and B is a system of p -sets (called blocks) from X such that each t -set is in exactly λ .

The aim of this paper is to investigate how far t – can be extended as well as establish and prove the existence / non – existence and hence, construct the t -quintuple system of balanced incomplete design when λ is varied and n and p are kept at a constant at 11 and 5 respectively.

The t- Designs

The Necessary Condition for the Existence of t- Design

Theorem 1

Suppose that a t - (n, p, λ) design B exists with $p = (p_1, \dots, p_m)$ and order $n = (n_1, \dots, n_m)$, with $|B| = b$. Then, for any m -tuple $t = (t_1, \dots, t_m)$ summing to t with $0 \leq t_i \leq k_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$, we have,

$$b \prod_{i=1}^m \binom{p-i}{t-i} = \lambda \prod_{i=1}^m \binom{n-i}{t-i} \quad (1)$$

and the Divisibility Condition for the Existence of t- Design is given as;

Theorem 2: In a t-(n, p, λ)-BIBD,

$$\binom{p-i}{t-i} \text{ is a divisor of } \lambda \binom{n-i}{t-i} \text{ for every } 0 \leq i \leq t-1 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is referred to as The Divisibility Theorem. The divisibility theorem posit that all designs that satisfy or obey it exist and all the designs that do not satisfy or obey it does not exist.

Methodology

Generation of Design Tuples

The first thing is to generate design tuples and they are generated according to which parameter or parameters is or are varied and the one or ones that is or are kept constant. In this work, t and λ will be rotated or varied while n and p will be kept constant, thus, for $2 \leq t \leq p$ and $\lambda = 1, \dots, p$, the tuples are generated from the relationship t-(n, p, λ) thus;

$$t - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= t - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix}, \quad t+1 - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots \quad t = p - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix}$$

This can also be give as

$$= p^{-3} - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix}, \quad p^{-2} - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix} \dots p^{-0} - \begin{pmatrix} n, & p & \lambda_1 \\ & & \lambda_2 \\ & & \cdot \\ & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \lambda_k \end{pmatrix}; \text{ if } p=i$$

Test of Obedience / Non –obedience of Design Tuples

After design tuples have been generated, each tuple has to be first subjected to a test to ascertain if it obeys the divisibility theorem or not using equation (2). Those that obey or satisfy the divisibility theorem for t-designs are classified as Obedient Designs (OD) while those that do not obey the theorem are classified as Non-obedient Designs (NOD).

Generation of Blocks

The blocks of the designs tuples are generated by method of combinatorics thus we have n combination p. This is written mathematically as

$$\binom{n}{p} \text{ or } \frac{(n)!}{(p)!(n-p)!} \quad (3)$$

and the blocks will be given as

$$b_1 \quad b_2 \quad b_3 \quad \dots \quad b_{\binom{n}{p}}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ p \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ p \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ p \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots \quad \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ p \end{pmatrix}$$

A design tuple is made up of several numbers of blocks of size, p and the number of replication, r, with the following relationships which is generally referred to as the necessary conditions for BIBDs;

$$(i) \quad bp = nr \quad (4)$$

$$(ii) \quad \lambda(n-1) = r(p-1) \quad (5)$$

And for the **t-Designs**, the parameters are related thus;

$$b \binom{p}{t} = \lambda \binom{n}{t} \quad (6)$$

Where; $b \geq n$ (and hence $r \geq p$) - (Fisher Inequality) $\lambda \geq 1$ and $p < n$

Construction of Designs

To construct a design is the last step in designs construction. This has to do with arranging together the blocks that suit or gives the design. Sometimes a design may exist and sometimes, it may not exist. After, arranging these blocks, the design is tested using the incidence matrix. The following recursive steps or algorithms are followed in constructing a t – Steiner quintuple balanced incomplete block design.

Step 1: Generate the designs tuples using combinatorics.

Step 2: Using the divisibility theorem given in equation (2), test each of the design tuples and classify them into obedient and non-obedient designs

Step 3: Generate all the blocks of the design using equation (3)

Step 4: Choose the group of designs (Obedient or Non-obedient) and construct each of them.

Step 5: Compute the number of blocks (b) and the number of replication (r) for the chosen design tuple using equation (5) and equation (3)

Step 6: To construct a design, first choose any block and carry out its $k(k-1)$ difference set algorithm (modulus) v for the set $(0 \dots\dots n-1)$.

The algorithm for the $k(k-1)$ difference set is given as ;

Let $X = Z_n$. Then the difference of two distinct element x and y in X is $\pm(x - y) := \pm |x - y|$ such that $1 \leq |x - y| \leq \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor$. The difference obtained in a set S , is the set of all difference of two distinct elements in S , denoted by $D(S) = \{x - y \pmod{n} \mid x, y \in S\}$.

Theorem 2.1: If C is a set of **Base or Initial block** of a $t - S(v, k, \lambda)$ design, $(X, B) = (Z_v, B)$, then $B = \{i + S \mid S \in C \text{ and } i \in Z_v\}$. (Note that if $S = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k\}$, then $i + S = \{x_1 + i, x_2 + i, \dots, x_k + i\} \pmod{n}$.)

Step 7: If the chosen block in step 6 satisfy the two condition above, then proceed to the next step, if not, choose another block and carry out step 7.

Step 8: Carry out a cyclic permutation to generate other blocks from the **initial or base block**.

The algorithm for cyclic permutation is given thus; δ of a set X , $\delta : x \rightarrow X$ s.t $i \in \mathfrak{y}$ then, $\delta(x) = x$ for any element of x . Let $S_i = \delta^i(s_0)$ for any $i \in \mathfrak{y}$. If S is finite and $k \geq 1$ for which $s_k = s_0$, then $s = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{k-1}\}$. The elements of $\delta = s_0 \rightarrow s_1 \rightarrow s_2 \dots \rightarrow s_{k-1} \rightarrow s_k = s_0$. That is $\delta(0) = 1, \delta(1) = 2, \delta(2) = 3, \delta(3) = 4, \delta(4) = 5, \delta(5) = 6, \delta(6) = 0, \dots$. This implies that from the initial block, add number to the initial blocks in a sequence of +1.

Step 9: Generate all the blocks (the blocks are in sizes, n) to have a design.

Step 10: Construct the **incidence matrix** for the design and use it to give the parameters of the design. Note that if the design incidence matrix does not give the parameters of the design, then it is not the design.

Step 11: Take another tuple and repeat the process until all the tuples are constructed.

Step 12: Tabulate the Existing and Non-Existing designs from the group of obedient designs.

Generation and Test of Design Tuples

We propose to construct some t -Steiner quintuple of balanced incomplete block designs of order 11 written as t -SQS(11, 5, λ). In this study, t and λ shall be varied while n and p shall be kept constant.

Generation of Design tuples for t -(11, 5, λ)

2 – (1 1, 5, 1)	3 – (1 1, 5, 1)	4 – (1 1, 5, 1)	5 – (1 1, 5, 1)
2 – (1 1, 5, 2)	3 – (1 1, 5, 2)	4 – (1 1, 5, 2)	5 – (1 1, 5, 2)
2 – (1 1, 5, 3)	3 – (1 1, 5, 3)	4 – (1 1, 5, 3)	5 – (1 1, 5, 3)
2 – (1 1, 5, 4)	3 – (1 1, 5, 4)	4 – (1 1, 5, 4)	5 – (1 1, 5, 4)
2 – (1 1, 5, 5)	3 – (1 1, 5, 5)	4 – (1 1, 5, 5)	5 – (1 1, 5, 5)

Test of Obedience and Non-Obedience

Using equation (2)

$$\binom{p-i}{t-i} = \lambda \binom{n-i}{t-i}; \text{ for every } 0 \leq i \leq t-1$$

Example 1.

2-S(11, 5, 2)

$$(n) = 11 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$$

Since, $t=2$, $i=0, 1$, $p=5$, $\lambda=2$

for $i=0$,

$$\binom{5}{2} = 2 \binom{11}{2}$$

$$10 = 2 \cdot 11 \cdot 5$$

\Rightarrow the RHS is a divisor of the LHS.

for $i=1$,

$$\binom{4}{1} = 2 \binom{10}{1}$$

$$4 = 2 \cdot 10$$

\Rightarrow the RHS is a divisor of the LHS.

Since the two systems showed that the RHS is a divisor of the LHS, we conclude that a 2-SQS(11, 5, 2) satisfies or obeys the divisibility theorem.

Example 2.

2-S(11, 5, 3)

$$(n) = 11 = \{0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10\}$$

Since, $t = 2, i = 0, 1, p = 5, \lambda = 3$

for $i = 0,$

$$\binom{5}{2} = 3 \binom{11}{2}$$

$$10 = 3 \cdot 11 \cdot 5$$

\Rightarrow the RHS is not a divisor of the LHS.

for $i = 1,$

$$\binom{4}{1} = 3 \binom{10}{1}$$

$$4 = 3 \cdot 10$$

\Rightarrow the RHS is not a divisor of the LHS.

Since the two systems showed that the RHS is not a divisor of the LHS, we conclude that a 2-S(11, 5, 3) does not satisfy or obeys the divisibility theorem.

The twenty tuples is then tabulated thus.

Table 1. Design that Obey the Divisibility Theorem (Obedient Design)

S/N	No of Pairs (t)	t-designs Type
1	2	2-(11, 5, 2)
2		2-(11, 5, 4)
3	3	3-(11, 5, 2)
4		3-(11, 5, 4)
5	4	4-(11, 5, 1)
6		4-(11, 5, 2)
7		4-(11, 5, 4)
8		4-(11, 5, 5)
9	5	5-(11, 5, 1)
10		5-(11, 5, 2)
11		5-(11, 5, 3)
12		5-(11, 5, 4)
13		5-(11, 5, 5)

Table 2. Design that do not Obey the Divisibility Theorem (Non –obedient Design)

S/N	No of Pairs (t)	t-designs Type
1	2	2-(11, 5, 1)
2		2-(11, 5, 3)

3		2-(11, 5, 5)
4	3	3-(11, 5, 1)
5		3-(11, 5, 3)
6		3-(11, 5, 5)
7	4	4-(11, 5, 3)

Construction from the Group of Obedient Designs

Generation of Blocks

From Equation (3), given that in this study, $n = 11$ and $p = 5$, then a total number of blocks for the construction equal to 462. Some will be useful while others will be thrown away.

Construction of Designs

Example. 2- S(11,5,2)

Following the steps in design construction, we have **02348** as **initial block**. By cyclic permutation we generate the 11 blocks thus;

(02348) (13459) (245610) (35670) (46781) (57892) (689103) (079104) (081015)
 (90126) (101237). And these blocks are represented thus;

B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	B ₅	B ₆	B ₇	B ₈	B ₉	B ₁₀	B ₁₁
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1	2
4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1	2	3
8	9	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

And the incidence matrix for the design is thus;

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

From the incidence matrix above, we see that $p(t_2, t_1), p(t_3, t_2), p(t_4, t_3), p(t_5, t_4), \dots, p(t_{10}, t_9)$, $= \lambda = 2$, $p = 5$, $r = 5$, and $N = 11$ which satisfies both the conditions for a BIBD and all the axioms of a 2- S(11,5,2)-Design. Thus, we have successfully constructed a 2 - S(11,5,2).

Determination of Block Size

From equation (5), we have

$$b \binom{p}{t} = \lambda \binom{n}{t}$$

$$b \binom{5}{2} = 2 \binom{11}{2}$$

$$\Rightarrow b = 11.$$

Determination of Number of Replications

From Equations (4) and (5)

$$bp = nr; \quad b = 11, n = 11 \text{ and } p = 5$$

$$\Rightarrow r = 5$$

Table 3. Summary of Existing Designs from the Group of Obedient Designs with Their Number of Blocks and Number of Replication

S/N	No of Pairs (t)	t-designs Type	No of Block	No of Groups of 11	No of Replications
1	2	2-(11, 5, 2)	11	1	5
2		2-(11, 5, 4)	22	2	10
3	3	3-(11, 5, 2)	33	3	15
4	4	4-(11, 5, 1)	66	6	30
5		4-(11, 5, 2)	132	12	60
6	5	5-(11, 5, 1)	11	1	5

Table 4. Summary of Non-Existing Designs from the Group of Obedient Designs

S/N	No of Pairs (t)	t-designs Type
1	3	3-(11, 5, 4)
2	4	4-(11, 5, 4)
3		4-(11, 5, 5)
4	5	5-(11, 5, 2)
5		5-(11, 5, 3)
6		5-(11, 5, 4)
7		5-(11, 5, 5)

Summary of Findings and Conclusions

Discussion of Findings

A total of twenty (20) design tuples from a t -Steiner quintuple systems of balanced incomplete block design written as t -SQS(11, 5, λ) were generated. From the number, thirteen (13) tuples satisfied or obeyed the divisibility theorem for t -designs and were classified as Obedient Designs (OD) while seven (7) tuples did not satisfy or obey the divisibility theorem, hence were classified as Non-Obedient Designs (NOD). However, when exploration on the obedient designs group were carried

out, it was discovered that of the thirteen (13) ODs, only six (6) were found to actually exist and were thus constructed with their number of blocks and replications determined. This discovery contradicts or set aside the earlier notion that all obedient designs or designs that satisfy the

divisibility theorem exists and can be constructed. Findings further established that a t-SQS(11, 5, λ) exists for $2 \leq t \leq 5$ and $1 \leq \lambda \leq 4$.

Conclusion

From the discussion of findings of this research above, we can conclude that for t-SQS(11, 5, λ)-balanced incomplete block designs, not all the designs that satisfy or obey the divisibility theorem exist. More than half, seven (7) out of thirteen (13) do not exist and hence cannot be constructed. This result shows that the divisibility theorem is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for the existence of t-Steiner quintuple systems BIBDs because some of the designs that obeyed the divisibility theorem and were assumed to exist do not exist in actuality.

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